

BuildingSmart Use-Case Definition – GIS Integrator for Digital Twin Based Asset Management

Section 1: MetaData

1.1 Identification of the document

Title:

GIS INTEGRATOR FOR DIGITAL TWIN BASED ASSET MANAGEMENT

ASHVIN: Assistants for Healthy, Safe and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin.

Short Text:

Data integration for condition assessment by categorization, and quantification of damages.

Project Status:

Finished

Publisher:

N/A

Authors:

Eser Senturk (Technische Universität Berlin), Mary Lidiya Kennedy (Technische Universität Berlin)

Introduction:

This document provides background and describes a use case of seamless integration of image data for purposes of condition assessment, categorization, and quantification of damages associated with infrastructure assets to effectively automate the process of damage detection and to geosition the identified damage for better asset management.

1.2 Imprint:

Project Group:

TUB, INFRAPLAN, CERTH

Partners:

Timo Hartmann Technische Universität Berlin), Irina Stipanovic (Infra Plan konzalting), Konstantinos Ioannidis (Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas), Stefanos Vrochidis (Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas)

Handling (can be edited based on preference):

N/A

Section 2: Use-Case Definition

2.1 Data Sheets & Standards

- Specifications of necessary standards and data sheets incorporated in the use-case.
- Airport Operational Database: The Airport Operational Database (AODB) serves as a fundamental IT system and a centralized repository housing comprehensive information pertaining to airport operations.
- Runway condition index as per ASTM for Airport Pavement Condition Index Surveys.

2.2 General Definition of the Use-Case

USE CASE DESCRIPTION	
Title	GIS Integrator For Digital-Twin-Based Asset Management Use Case
Goal	To integrate the data related to monitoring, condition assessment and maintenance of infrastructures into GIS for asset management on all levels and to categorize and quantify damages.
Description	To integrate image data for purposes of condition assessment, categorization, and quantification of damages associated with infrastructure assets to effectively automate the process of damage detection and to geoposition the identified damage for better asset management.
Input Data	Image data, BIM model describing the asset.
Sequence of actions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collate the image monitoring data from the site to train and evaluate the automated machine learning defect detection model. 2. Define the different types of damages that are to be detected or are of a common occurrence concerning the asset under study. 3. Filter the dataset to remove images that are not relevant to damage detection. 4. The dataset is divided into a training (80%) and testing set (20%). 5. The filtered image is then annotated with defect instances of interests as classified. 6. The annotated images are then processed to fine tune thereby optimizing pixel dimensions for training and testing. 7. This annotated dataset is employed to train the detection model and validate its efficiency through relative accuracy metrics known as Intersection-over-Union. 8. The acquired images are processed by the developed Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) detection model and a prediction mask is provided, where the detected defects are highlighted. The fine-tuned model is then tested with the test data set and is evaluated for accuracy and qualitative prediction. 9. The detection outcome is then combined with other valuable results such as information about the location, the number, the type, and the size of the defects. 10. The images acquired from the site can also be exploited to generate an Ortho mosaic representation of the scanned area for digital representation of the asset. 11. All the forementioned elements in a consolidated map facilitate estimation of the severity of the damages and monitoring of their evolution over time.

Primary actors	Asset owners or managers.
Secondary actors	Maintenance engineers, structural engineers
Pre-conditions	Adequate amount of good quality image data of the site under study for monitoring and condition assessment
Trigger	Digitalisation and automation of the inspection and condition assessment of assets
Post-conditions	
Frequency of use	Throughout the lifecycle of the asset- especially during its maintenance cycle
Support planned for	ASHVIN
UC Created by	INFCON, CERTH
Date of last update	

Figure 1 Use Case Description

Aim and Scope:

The proposed use case aims to integrate image monitoring data associated with assessment and maintenance of infrastructure assets into GIS for asset management. The use case proposes a framework to assess, categorize and quantify damages of assets which can thereby assist managers to develop maintenance strategies for long term as well as short term. The current use case aids in automatizing risk assessment of the assets , and preparation of cost estimation for maintenance and proposals for future maintenance assessment and scheduling.

Objectives:

A GIS application as proposed in the current use case enables asset managers to monitor the anticipated state of various assets based on their digital twins using a set of asset management key performance indicators. Utilizing a visualization, maintenance schedules may be designed with a thorough understanding of an asset's status, the corresponding output can be used to develop a risk model which considers different maintenance strategies and allows end-users to interactively review and utilize specific outputs of the risk assessment and the consequence modelling in the risk analysis.

2.3 Overall Process:

The overall process map for the current use case based on GIS application is shown in Fig 2.

Figure 2 Process Map

Fig 2 gives a comprehensive overview of the processes and steps involved in the current use case. The first step is to acquire image monitoring data from the asset site by employing sensor or UAV drones. This can also constitute historical image monitoring data accumulated over a period. This is followed of different types of defects of interest and their potential failure mechanisms.

The main objective of the proposed method is to detect different types of surface defects enclosed in visual data, collected through a UAV scanning mission over the asset under study. The current approach is conceived as a two-step deployment process. The acquisition of visual data for the purpose of implementing and testing UNet based Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models is referred to as the offline phase. In this respect, A UAV can be employed to conduct a coverage mission across the infrastructure asset and capture RGB images displaying surface defects. The collected data is then analysed and annotated appropriately based on expert judgment, labelling the defect instances of interest as defined and categorized. This annotated dataset is used to train the detection model and test the efficiency of the model through relative accuracy metrics. It should be emphasized that transfer learning techniques can also be used in this stage, employing suitable data sets from other sites or photographs obtained from prior infrastructure monitoring missions over the asset, regularizing the requirement of collecting new data.

The CNN model, which semantically separates presented defect instances, is the key element of the proposed system. A prominent network for image semantic segmentation, the UNet architecture, serves as the foundation for the proposed approach. The encoder and the decoder are the two primary components of the specific architecture. The encoder's aim is to enclose the input image in a condensed representation that nonetheless holds high-level information. To accomplish this, a series of successive convolutional layers are deployed to gradually diminish the input's spatial dimensions while increasing the input's number of channels (depth) in order to enhance the encoded vector's information content.

The decoder, on the contrary, seeks to retrieve the segmented output from the encoded representation. In the way, the depth of the encoded vector is gradually decreased while the encoded vector is up sampled to match the original spatial dimensions by combining convolutional layers and interpolation. The preceding process generates the segmented output, in which a class identification is assigned to each image pixel. The model uses skip connections between the layers of the encoder and decoder to boost model efficiency. This architecture ensures that information is seamlessly back propagated to the initial layers of the network while providing critical low-level function to the network's latest levels.

The real-time operation of the proposed methodology is referred to as the online phase. In this instance, the developed detection model processes the RGB pictures acquired during the UAV flight and generates a prediction mask that highlights the detected defects. The results of the detection can be integrated with other relevant information to enhance the inspection process. The segmented outcome can be utilized to extract characteristics regarding the size, type, quantity, and location of defects that were identified. This followed by integration of the GIS software to geolocate the defects identified in the images. GIS can manage and analyse geospatial data. As part of the data exchange, provide the GIS system with the geotagged images. The GIS system will use the GPS coordinates to map the images onto the geographical area of interest. This is achieved by overlaying the detected defect locations onto GIS maps by matching the GPS coordinates in the image metadata with the GIS database. This will provide a geospatial context for the defects. Additionally, the captured RGB data may be utilized to produce an orthomosaic image of the scanned region, which may then be used to develop a digital representation map of the infrastructure. Further the probability of failure of the identified damages can be calculated depending on the nature of the defect under, an example of this is later explained in the demo of this document. Combining the aforementioned data into a comprehensive digital map enables objective, digital tracking of the damages' temporal progress as well as estimation of the severity level of the investigated damages.

Implementation on #3: Zadar Airport Runway in Croatia

Zadar Airport is situated in the middle of the Adriatic coast, and in 2019 was among the top 5 in terms of traffic growth (+37,6%) increase in passenger traffic EUROPE Airport Traffic Report, www.aci-europe.org). The airport was opened in 1969 as an addition to the existing military runway, and with the construction of a civilian runway, it became the only airport in Croatia with two runways. The airport had a steady growth of traffic during the 1970s and 1980s, when tourism in Croatia, and especially in Dalmatia, reached its peak at the time. However, this was abruptly interrupted by the war in Croatia in the first half of the 1990s, when the Zadar airport was occupied and destroyed, with severely damaged terms. After the war the airport was repaired.

Airport infrastructure, which includes all operational areas for receiving and dispatching passengers and aircraft, was built, as already stated above, almost 50 years ago. In that period there were several partial renovations of asphalt surfaces, but no major reconstructions. This means that the essential infrastructure of the airport including runways is not in a very good condition degrading further rapidly, starting to influence the safety of traffic. The digital twin asset management tool was comprising of the GIS integrator with the defect detection model used to improve the overall operational and maintenance management, consequently, optimize the resources spending and improve safety.

The main idea for this demonstration project is the use of images of operational areas of the airport collected with unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). In this demo, a digital twin is developed containing detailed structure information about the runway layout, materials, drainage systems and signage in BIM format. It will be combined with the Airport Operational Database (AODB) and inspection data performed with Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs).

To categorize and quantify damages of the airport runway, it was identified to acquire large data sets from monitoring and inspection about infrastructure performance, which in our case was recorded by UAVs (unmanned aerial vehicles) and used them as inputs for AI models. Deep machine learning techniques are then applied on drone-based images for the automation of the visual inspection and damage detection procedures. The first step in the methodology is a determination of runway condition index, which is following ASTM for Airport Pavement Condition Index Surveys(cite), this step is crucial to define and choose various defects of interest and their potential failure mechanisms which in turn aid development maintenance and repair strategies. This is achieved by deployment UAVs at the site, focusing on the pre-dominant types of defects, caused by load, climate, and/or poor construction, or a combination of these in a form of cracks (D1), repaired cracks (D2) and construction joints (D3). Based on the expert judgment the level of severity of the recorded defects were categorized in three groups, low, medium and high, in order to determine the Deduct Value (DV) and finally Pavement Condition Index (PCI) for each sample unit, following the ASTM methodology, as follows: $PCI = 100 - DV$

PCI represents a numerical rating of the pavement condition that ranges from 0 to 100 with 0 being the worst possible condition and 100 being the best possible condition. In Table II modified PCI classification is presented. Based on the detection of defects on the pavement's surface, the runway condition index gives a measure of the pavement's current condition. The structural

capacity cannot be directly measured by this index, but it offers a rational and impartial basis for choosing the most important maintenance and repair tasks. Rating scale for the PCI, as a percentage of the sample area with certain defect class detected.

Figure 3 Qualitative results of the deployed defect detection method. Cracks are highlighted with red, repaired cracks with blue, construction joints with yellow and tire marks with green colour, respectively

Colour	Runway condition index PCI	Rating
	80-100	Excellent
	60-80	Adequate
	40-60	Poor
	0-40	Unsatisfactory

Figure 4 Runway Categorization based on Pavement Condition Index

Colour	Tyre marks density (%)	Rating
	0-30	Excellent
	30-50	Adequate
	50-100	Unsatisfactory

Figure 5 Runway Categorization based on Tyre Mark Density

Deep machine learning techniques are then applied on drone-based images for the automation of the visual inspection and damage detection procedures. The developed methodology for digitalization and automation of inspection and monitoring processes of operational areas, are then integrated into GIS based predictive maintenance tool. Collected data is transformed into single PIs and eventually combined into four KPIs productivity, costs, resource efficiency and health and safety. Final intention is to integrate use of UAVs into continuous monitoring practice and risk-based maintenance planning.

Processing of dataset: The developed dataset acquired from the site contains RGB images collected through two different phases. In the first phase, hand-held cameras were utilized to capture numerous defect instances observed on the surface of the airport's runway. In total, 301 high-resolution images of variable size were collected. In the second phase, a camera mounted on a UAV was utilized to capture visual data from a wider area of the runway. During the flight mission, 100 high resolution images of size 4000 x 3000 pixels, were captured. The images collected through the two aforementioned phases were joint into a pluralistic dataset containing 401 high-quality images enclosing a wide range of defect instances under varying capturing conditions. Following stakeholder guidance, 5 classes were defined, namely crack, joint (repaired cracks), construction joint, tire marks and background. The annotation process was conducted by field-experts. The developed dataset was utilized to train and test the designed model. In specific, 20% of the drone images were randomly selected for testing while the rest 80%, combined with the data of the first phase, was used for training.

Development, training, testing of defect detection model: The CNN model designed for the defect detection task, EfficientNet , a state-of-the-art architecture, pretrained on ImageNet [24], was utilized as the backbone. Using EfficientNet in the encoding stage of the UNet architecture aims at extracting robust high-level features while preserving a balanced trade-off between prediction accuracy and inference time. The developed model was trained for 2000 epochs with a batch size 16. A set of image processing techniques was employed for data augmentation. In specific, input images are randomly (with probability 50%) flipped horizontal/vertical, rescaled and modified in terms of brightness. Finally, a patch of 256 x 256 pixels is cropped from a random position of the input image. Training was performed with Adam optimizer with learning rate equal to 10⁻³. Regarding the loss function, focal loss was employed, since it is designed to deal with cases of unbalanced datasets.

Evaluation of ML model

The efficiency of the developed defect detection model is measured using Intersection-over-Union (IoU), a well-known metric used to evaluate semantic segmentation methods. Aiming to achieve a thorough validation, the splitting to training and testing set is repeated 3 times and the deployed model is trained and evaluated on the corresponding sets, accordingly. Since the original resolution of testing images is quite high, non-overlapping tiles of 512 x 512 pixels are fed to the trained model and then resynthesized to the segmented outcome. IoU is measured for the entire testing dataset of the segmented images and is reported for each class in Table III. Mean IoU (mIoU) refers to the average IoU over the 5 classes.

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<i>Split</i>	<i>Crack</i>	<i>Repair. crack</i>	<i>Constr. Joint</i>	<i>Tyre Marks</i>	<i>Back- ground</i>	<i>mIoU</i>
1	18.72	35.00	49.80	68.22	96.68	53.68
2	21.71	37.36	29.40	69.30	97.71	51.09
3	20.67	39.13	44.40	63.28	95.95	52.68

Figure 6 Evaluation results in terms IoU(%) for each class

Although the developed model can effectively detect most classes, the results suggest the challenging nature of the problem. With respect to crack and joints classes, the method can detect the depicted instances, however, it shows lower accuracy into identifying at pixel-level their exact shape and size. This remains a challenging task, due to the complex shape and the ambiguous contours of these classes. Considering construction joints, the model can effectively distinguish them from the joint instances, although these two classes differ only in shape (construction joints are usually straight elongated lines), while texture characteristics are the same for both of them. As for the rest of the classes, the model reports higher performance since they refer to less difficult cases. Tire marks have distinctive shape and size, and they can be clearly differentiated from the background textures. Regarding background class, the high IoU values are due to the significantly higher number of samples. In total, it should be noted that the developed model can provide sufficient information on the defects recorded during online inspections, fulfilling the main objective of recognizing the type of defects and identifying their main "skeleton" by giving an estimation of their shape and size.

The visual results indicate that in most cases the model developed can efficiently detect the captured defects. The segmentation is more accurate for classes such as tyre marks (green) and construction joints (yellow). This is due to their natural shape and size combined with their texture characteristics that ease the distinction background. Regarding repaired cracks (blue) class, the model can efficiently detect relevant instances, especially in cases where they are distinct clearly from the background. Some mislabeled repaired cracks as construction joints or vice versa, hint at the challenges of a real-world operating framework. It is worth noting that the texture of these two classes is identical and they only differ in terms of shape and size. Considering cracks (red) class, although there are cases where the deployed model cannot identify the crack shape in full extent, the illustrated instances are adequately recognized.

Figure 7 Qualitative results of the deployed defect detection method. Cracks are highlighted with red, repaired cracks with blue, construction joints with yellow and tire marks with green colour, respectively

Online phase:

All the images collected through UAV survey of the Zadar airport runway are geositioned. By running all the images through the defect detection model, all detected defects have been associated with local coordinates, which then were transformed into global coordinates and presented in GIS application. Map of the runway area is shown with red dots presenting all the images collected by UAV camera and enlarged image with the results of the defect detection using pretrained ML model. Each analysed image was divided into 16 sample units with approximate area of 13.4 m². Condition of the runway pavement sample units, defined with PCI value, was determined according to the adopted ASTM methodology and visualized with color-coding as described in the methodology section. The results of the PCI calculations are presented in Fig. 5. The results of tyre mark density calculation and categorization of runway SU are presented in Table 4. From the identified, geositioned and quantified damages, PCI can be calculated as per Equation 1. Each analysed image was divided into 16 sample units with approximate area of 13.4 m². Condition of the runway pavement sample units, defined with PCI value, was determined according to the adopted ASTM methodology and visualized with color-coding as described in the methodology section. The results of the PCI calculations are presented in Table 4 and graphically presented in Fig. 5. The results of tyre mark density calculation and categorization of runway SU are presented in fig. 6.

Figure 8 Map of the runway with GIS positioned photographs

SU	Length			Area (m ²)	PCI N	Tyre mark density %
	Crack	Repaired crack	Construction joint			
	(m)	(m)	(m)			
1	-	-	3.21	-	65	0.0
2	-	-	3.74	0.04	64	0.3
3	-	-	3.10	-	66	0.0
4	-	0.59	3.42	-	42	0.0
5	-	-	-	8.05	100	59.9
6	-	-	-	8.50	100	63.3
7	-	-	-	7.95	100	59.2
8	-	0.09	-	8.65	91	64.4
9	-	8.34	2.52	4.52	3	33.6
10	0.62	10.32	3.24	4.07	0	30.3
11	0.47	7.74	3.48	4.63	0	34.5
12	0.73	6.06	3.22	4.48	0	33.4
13	-	4.82	2.58	5.74	11	42.7
14	0.43	4.39	2.85	7.16	0	53.3
15	-	2.56	2.89	7.09	20	52.8
16	0.16	3.25	2.97	6.33	0	47.1

Figure 9 PCI and Tyre Mark Density per Sample Unit(SU)

Figure 10 Categorization of runway condition using adopted PCI rating based on detected defects cracks, repaired cracks, and construction joints

Figure 11 Categorization of runway surface condition using based on the percentage of area covered with tyre marks

Measurable performance indicators for the current use case

Performance indicators	Unit	How to measure	Proposed integration into Digital Twin
Key Performance Indicator: Productivity			
Duration of inspection activity- Productivity	h, days	Duration of inspection affects users. For large airport runways requires partial closures or full closures of a bridge. Time required for inspection can be used for the calculation of user delays (decreased speed, detour) through appropriate calculations.	Inspection time: drone flight vs. inspection with traffic closures, duration, user delay costs
Key Performance Indicator: Resource Efficiency			
Environmental impacts related to the usage of drones vs. vehicles	CO2, SO2, PO43, Sb,... €/kg, m2, unit or total	Different environmental impact categories for energy / fuel usage to compare for: Drone – battery size Vehicle type, duration of inspection	LCA model outputs Graphical representation (of comparison results)
Environmental impacts related to the unavailability of the asset	CO2, SO2, PO43, Sb,... €/day or hour	Congestions of traffic or detours (longer routes than without traffic regulation for maintenance intervention) cause increased CO2 emissions which are transferred into monetary units allowing comparison of different interventions.	Traffic data / congestions / delays Cameras LCA
Key Performance Indicator: cost			
Inspection cost	€/m2, unit or total	Includes cost of equipment, energy, and workforce. Comparison drone vs. conventional inspection	Cost data over time, graphs
User delay cost	€/min, h	The traffic delay costs are the costs that represent the valuable time of the network/bridge users themselves.	Cost data per activity Can be visualised based on traffic data and duration time
Total LCC	€/kg, m2, unit or total	For calculation of total LCC a life cycle scenario needs to be developed with prospects of deterioration and timing of certain maintenance interventions.	Annual cost per scenario

2.4 Disciplines:

Investigation discipline- risk assessment.

Project Management discipline- cost estimation, proposal preparation, and scheduling

2.5 Life Cycle Stages:

Operation and maintenance

Section 3: Process-definition

Life cycle stages: post-construction stage

Operation and maintenance

Section 4: Exchange Requirements

The current section gives a brief description of the data exchange requirements for utilizing the current use case.

Figure 12 Exchange Requirements

1. Data Collection and Preparation: Images

Collect high-resolution images of the infrastructure asset using drones, cameras, or other imaging devices and tag the images with geospatial information, including GPS coordinates and orientation data.

2. Defect Detection with ML:

The collected image data should be preprocessed to improve the performance of the model optimizing pixel dimensions for training and testing. Export the model architecture and parameters such as U-Net configuration, learning rate, batch size to the IoT platform for further deployment and inference.

3. GIS integrator:

Export the geotagged images with detected defects from the ML model to the GIS system. This can be done by providing the GIS system with a CSV or similar file that includes image filenames, GPS coordinates, and defect information (e.g., defect type, severity).

4. BIM Integration:

If applicable, integrate BIM data into the process. BIM contains detailed 3D models and information about the asset's components and structure. The BIM data can be used to validate and enhance the understanding of defect locations. Integrate BIM with GIS to create a comprehensive view of the asset.

5. Data Fusion and Visualization:

Combine the ML-detected defect information (from step 2) with GIS and BIM data to create a unified view. Visualize the infrastructure asset, defects, and their geospatial context in the GIS system. This integration provides a holistic understanding of the asset's condition.

6. Reporting and Maintenance Planning:

Generate reports within the GIS system that include the location, type, and severity of defects, along with their geospatial context. Use these reports to prioritize and plan maintenance and repair activities. The data exchange between the GIS system and maintenance planning tools can help streamline this process

7. Continuous Monitoring:

Implement continuous monitoring using drones or sensors to capture new images and data regularly. Update the ML model with new data for ongoing defect detection. Share this updated model output with the GIS system for real-time tracking of defects.

Section 5: Change Log

This is a section only for changes made after publishing to the front end